

Passive Microwave Remote Sensing with the Synthetic Aperture Radiometer, ESTAR, during the Southern Great Plains Experiment

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ABSTRACT

Results are presented of measurements made by the synthetic aperture radiometer, ESTAR, during the Southern Great Plains experiment in Oklahoma during the summer, 1997. The objective of the Southern Great Plains experiment (SGP97) was to study passive microwave remote sensing of soil moisture on a spatial and temporal scale representative of future observations from space. To this end, ESTAR flew at high altitude (7.6 km) and mapped a swath about 50 km wide (east-to-west) and about 300 km long. The area mapped extended west from Oklahoma City to El Reno and north from the Little Washita River watershed to the Oklahoma-Kansas border. Data was collected almost daily for one month (from June 17 to July 17) and includes several examples of wetting by rainfall followed by a period of drying.

THE SOUTHERN GREAT PLAINS EXPERIMENT

The Southern Great Plains Experiment (SGP97) originated in an experiment proposed for the ESTAR radiometer called "Soil Moisture Mapping at Satellite Temporal and Spatial Scales". It was planned to map a large area east of Oklahoma City to simulate data which would be obtained with a sensor in space. The objective was to assess remote sensing at the scale expected from space and to establish that soil moisture retrieval algorithms, developed at the local scale (individual fields), could be extended to the coarser resolution expected from a future sensor in space. This research was an outgrowth of an earlier experiment at the Little Washita Watershed which demonstrated the potential for new insight to be expected from mapping large areas [1,2]. By the time it began in June 1997, SGP97 had grown to include an

extensive network of surface measurements, several aircraft with remote sensing instruments, and a major research effort to study of the effect of soil moisture on the evolution of the atmospheric boundary layer.

ESTAR

The electronically scanned thinned array radiometer (ESTAR) is a synthetic aperture microwave radiometer operating at a center frequency of 1.413 GHz (L-band) with a bandwidth of 25 MHz, an integration time of about 0.25 seconds, and horizontal polarization [1,4]. Aperture synthesis is an interferometric technique in which the product (complex correlation) of the output voltage from pairs of antennas is measured at many different baselines. Each baseline produces a sample point in the Fourier transform of the scene and a map of the scene is obtained after all measurements have been made by inverting the transform. ESTAR (Figure 1) is a hybrid of a real and a synthetic aperture radiometer. It uses a real aperture (stick antennas) to obtain resolution along track and aperture synthesis (correlation between pairs of sticks) to obtain resolution across track. ESTAR is an engineering research tool developed at the University of Massachusetts and Goddard Space Flight Center to study the potential of aperture synthesis to enable future high resolution microwave radiometry from space [3,4].

Calibration of ESTAR is achieved by viewing two scenes of known brightness temperature. A regression, comparing the measured response with the theoretical response, is used to determine the gain and bias needed for calibration [2]. To check calibration during the aircraft missions, a blackbody was measured before and after each flight and a water target (lake) was viewed during the flight.

EXPERIMENT

During SGP97, the ESTAR instrument was flown on the NASA P-3 aircraft operated by the Wallops Flight Facility. Flights were conducted at an altitude of about 7.6 km (25 kft). The original flight plan called for 4 parallel flight lines covering an area extending westward from Oklahoma City to El Reno and extending from south of the Little Washita Watershed northward to the Oklahoma-Kansas border (Figure 2). These flight lines are about 300 km long and spaced about 12 km apart. The first modification of the flight lines was the addition of an extension on the northern end (of the two most eastern lines) to provide coverage of the CASES study area. These CASES lines (flight lines 8 and 9 in Figure 1) were flown four times during SGP97 (June 20, July 2, 12 and 16). In addition, two east-west flight lines were added at the latitude of Oklahoma City to overcome a problem with RFI associated with Will Rogers Airport. With one exception, the flight lines were flown beginning in the upper northwestern corner (line 1) and flying south, picking up line 2 at its southern end and flying north, etc. The east-west lines between Oklahoma City and El Reno (lines 5 and 6) were flown by interrupting line 4 in the vicinity of Will Rogers airport and then flying from east-to-west along line 5 and returning to line 4 from west-to-east along line 6. The flight was resumed along the northern extension of line 4 which was renumbered to be line 7 (Figure 2). Just to the east of the northern end of Line 7 were two small lakes (Sooner Lake and Kaw Lake) which were used as reference scenes for calibration.

ESTAR arrived in Oklahoma City on June 16 and data collection began the next day, June 17. In total, data were collected on 22 of the 30 days the aircraft was deployed in Oklahoma. Nominal mission times were take-off at 9:30 am and landing at 12:30 pm. Weather conditions (thunder storms) forced changes in the flight plan on a few days and ESTAR was down five days for equipment repairs. The CASES lines (lines 8 and 9) were flown at the end of the regular mission and required about an additional one-half hour.

RESULTS

Figure 3 shows ESTAR images from a four day period (July 10-13) toward the end of the experiment. The image at the beginning of this sequence was made on July 10, which was the last several warm dry days (no rain). There was rain on the evening of July 10 continuing into July 11. Lingering severe weather from the storm on the evening of July 10 caused some of the lines to be shortened on July 11. (As a result, the four lines which make up the image for July 11 are clearly evident at the bottom.)

Cooler microwave brightness temperatures due to the rain are evident on July 11. On July 12 the regular mission plus the extended lines into Kansas were flown. There was no rain on July 12 or 13 and the image on July 13 indicates continued drying of the study area (warmer brightness temperatures) from the rain on July 10-11. This pattern of cool brightness temperatures followed by a transition to warmer brightness temperatures as the soil dried occurred several times during the month-long experiment.

Ground sampling of soil moisture in the area mapped by ESTAR was concentrated in the Little Washita Watershed (23 locations), the ARS grasslands research facility at El Reno (16 sites west of Oklahoma City) and the ARM CART central facility near Lamont (10 sites). A comparison of the ESTAR brightness temperature with soil moisture measurements at these "surface truth" sites is underway (incomplete at the writing of this paper). However, a comparison at the watershed level for the Little Washita Watershed (southern end of the study area) has been made. In particular, the watershed average surface soil moisture (i.e. average of all surface monitoring sites) has been plotted against the average of the ESTAR brightness temperature map for the same area. ESTAR mapped this watershed previously for 8 days in 1992 [1,2] and again 4 times in 1994 under similar circumstances (same altitude and aircraft platform). Plotting the data from these previous experiments with the data obtained in SGP97 yields good agreement and provides a consistency check on the SGP97 data.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1: Imaging with the ESTAR radiometer. Resolution is obtained with real aperture (stick antennas) along track and by means of aperture synthesis cross track.

Figure 2: Flight lines for the SGP97 experiment. Lake calibration site is indicated as well as Oklahoma City, where the aircraft was stationed.

Figure 3: ESTAR images of brightness temperature for July 10-13. Darker tones indicate cooler brightness temperature (wetter soil). Rain occurred in the evening between July 10 and July 11. The three small dark spots south and west of Oklahoma City are lakes.